

Hybrid Geometric Similarity and Local Consistency Measure for GPR Hyperbola Detection

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Abstract. The recent development of novel powerful sensor topologies, namely Ground Penetrating Radar (GPR) antennas, gave a thrust to the modeling of underground environment. An important step towards underground modelling is the detection of the typical hyperbola patterns on 2D images (B-scans), formulated due to the reflections of underground utilities. This work introduces a soil-agnostic approach for hyperbola detection, starting from one dimensional GPR signals, viz. A-scans, to perform a segmentation of each trace into candidate reflection pulses. Feature vector representations are calculated for segmented pulses through multilevel DWT decomposition. A theoretical geometric model of the corresponding hyperbola pattern is generated on the image plane for all point coordinates of the area under inspection. For each theoretical model, measured pulses that best support it are extracted and are utilized to validate it with a novel hybrid measure. The novel measure simultaneously controls the geometric plausibility of the examined hyperbola model and the consistency of the pulses contributing to this model across all the examined A-scan traces. Implementation details are discussed and experimental evaluation is exhibited on real GPR data.

Keywords: Hyperbola detection · GPR imaging, · soil agnostic detection

1 Introduction

Recently, significant advancements in underground sensing through GPR antennas have been introduced by the respective scientific community that enabled modelling of large subsurface areas [5, 10]. The latter, brought a new era in the nondestructive inspection techniques that significantly reduced the construction costs [4]. However, the automatic analysis of GPR data for the detection of subsurface utilities remains an active research topic. This is due to the fact, that even if the synchronous arrays of GPR antennas can produce massive data of the underground environment, most of their annotation is still performed manually or at least requires human verification after the application of a automatic

utilities detection method [9]. The most typical processing of GPR data for the detection of underground utilities relies on the image processing techniques applied on B-scans, which are also known as radargrams and are 2D images formulated by gathering A-scan measurements along the GPR antenna motion, for the detection and isolation of reflection signatures [16, 15]. In particular, due to specific geometry of scanning sessions, consistent utilities are expected to shape hyperbolic patterns on B-scans. Consequently, utility detection has been mostly tackled as a hyperbola detection problem. In the past, several computer vision techniques, that utilized hand-crafted features, have been utilized to this end and specifically Histograms of Oriented Gradients have been proven robust descriptors of the orientation of recorded reflections [16, 18]. Fitting hyperbolic shape has also been treated as an optimization problem, approached by Genetic Algorithms [13] and Neural Networks [1]. Recent works indicate successful application of Sparse Representation to gas pipe localization [17], while state of the art learning techniques such as traditional Convolutional Neural Networks [8] and sophisticated variations optimized towards balancing computational load and accuracy (Faster Region Convolutional Neural Network) [6] have been reported to perform well on detection and classification tasks respectively. Moreover, the work presented in [7] illustrates how a hyperbola detection module can be integrated into a complete underground modelling system. In the current method, a hybrid measure that captures (i) geometric similarity of recorded pulses to a theoretic model and (ii) consistency of those pulses has been developed. At the core of the approach presented herein is the Discrete Wavelet Transform (DWT) decomposition. The DWT is a powerful tool applied in signal processing domains, suitable for the frequency analysis of non-stationary signals, such as GPR signals. Successful application of DWT for filtering and denoising purposes of GPR data has been reported in [11] [3], while the authors of [14] applied wavelet analysis in order to perform GPR data classification. In current work DWT decomposition is utilized to extract a feature representation of reflection pulses.

2 Method Description

2.1 Peak Detection and Segmentation

The proposed method commences with the isolation of the most prominent regions on the B-scan that could correspond to a hyperbolic apex. This first processing step is applied in a column-wise manner operating thus on the A-scans, i.e. the separate columns of a B-scan. Each such column corresponds to the time-domain measurements captured by the GPR device at a specific location. A stimulating pulse is transmitted by the GPR antenna and reflections of the pulse originating from underground obstacles travel back to the GPR receiver. Hence, recorded signal is a composition of time-shifted (due to the travel distance) and corrupted (due to noisy nature of underground signal propagation) instances of the initial pulse. This pulse usually closely resembles to a Ricker wavelet, which is also mentioned as Mexican hat wavelet, a name indicative of

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Fig. 1. a) Highlighted segmented pulse defined by one of the peaks on an A-scan
b) Normalized extracted pulse and the DWT coefficients that constitute its feature representation.

its waveform, that is centered around a positive peak value. Reflection pulses of an A-scan are expected to have similar waveforms. Therefore, positive peak values along the recorded A-scan are indicators of the existence of waveforms caused by underground reflections of the original pulse. Although the center point is as good as any other point of the Ricker wavelet to characterize the whole waveform, positive peak values are easy to be defined and detected along a signal trace. Peak values of the recorded $y[t]$ trace are computed by transforming the $y[t]$ recorded signal into the frequency domain. Fast Fourier Transform is utilized and $j \cdot \omega \cdot Y[\omega]$ and $-\omega^2 \cdot Y[\omega]$ formulas are applied to calculate first and second derivatives. Finally, first and second derivative checks and a sign check are applied to locate local maxima positive values. It should be noted that most of these values correspond to artifacts of the scanning procedure, underground clutter, etc. and only few of them reflect the existence of actual underground utilities. However, a significant reduction in the search space of candidate hyperbola apexes is achieved by isolating these peak values on each A-scan. In Fig. 1(a) an example of a GPR trace along with the detected positive peaks is illustrated. The initial trace has 970 samples and 83 peaks are detected along it. The set of peaks is more than 10 times smaller than the set of all the time samples. The rest of the pipeline benefits from this reduction, since all the rest steps are applied on the former set. For each peak a pulse of a predefined length, centered around it, is extracted. The length of the extracted pulses is defined in accordance with the working frequency F_o of the GPR scanning device. Frequencies of reflections are expected to fall symmetrically within a band centered around the central frequency and a rule of thumb is to consider the width of the band equal to $1.5 \cdot F_o$. Consequently, the interval of relevant measured frequencies is the following: $[0.25 \cdot F_o, 1.75 \cdot F_o]$. The low frequency of the band defines the largest expected duration of a single reflection pulse in time. This duration in combination with the sampling frequency F_s of the scanning GPR device determines the number of time samples that need to be considered in order to successfully extract a complete waveform of a reflection pulse from the rest of the GPR trace. In our case the original trace is segmented into pulses of

length equal to 31 time samples that are centered around each detected peak. An example of an extracted pulse is illustrated in Fig. 1(a).

2.2 Discrete Wavelet Transform decomposition

For each extracted pulse a feature representation is calculated by utilizing the multilevel Discrete Wavelet Transform (DWT) decomposition of a 1D signal. In one level of the DWT the entry signal $y[n]$ (A-scan) is convolved with a high pass filter $h[n]$ and a low pass filter $g[n]$ and is in both cases subsequently down-sampled by two, producing the detail and the approximation coefficients respectively. On the multilevel DWT, approximation coefficients are provided to the next level and the same procedure is repeated. The maximum number of levels the above procedure can be repeated is determined by the length of the original signal and the number of coefficients of the applied filters. From one level to the next one, due to the filtering and the subsampling, the frequency band is reduced to half and at the same time the frequency resolution is doubled. The high-pass filters $h[n]$ comprise the child wavelets of the mother wavelet function and are computed from:

$$\psi_{j,k}[t] = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2^j}} \psi\left[\frac{t - k2^j}{2^j}\right] \quad (1)$$

where j is the scale parameter accounting for the level of resolution and k is the shift parameter. Low-pass $g[n]$ filters are produced by a function which is referred as a scaling function. The wavelet family that has been chosen here is Daubechies-6 due to the resemblance of the mother wavelet function to the emitted GPR pulse [2]. Once the decomposition reaches the maximum level, the detail coefficients of all levels along with the approximation coefficients of the maximum level constitute a sparse representation of the signal, which is perfectly invertible and captures information both for frequency and time domain. A feature vector that comprises all detail coefficients and approximation coefficients of the maximum level is formulated for each isolated pulse centered around a peak. In Fig. 1(b) the DWT decomposition of the extracted pulse of Fig. 1(a) is demonstrated.

2.3 Generation of Hyperbolic Templates

Having computed the features for all examined pulses centered around the extracted peak values from all A-scans, the rest of the processing is applied on the 2D space of the B-scan image. The Y axis of a B-scan image represents the time axis of the GPR traces and temporal sampling frequency defines the dy step of this axis (difference in time between two consecutive recorded values). The X axis represents the distance covered by the GPR device along its scanning trajectory and spatial sampling frequency defines the dx step of this axis (distance between two consecutive recorded traces). According to the point reflector concept [12], the pattern formed on a B-scan image from reflections originating

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Fig. 2. a) Travel distances schematic of the GPR signal on consecutive scanning positions. b) Left: hyperbola templates corresponding to utilities at different depths on the same position along the scanning trajectory, Right: hyperbola templates corresponding to utilities at the same depth on three different positions along the scanning trajectory.

from an underground utility, that lies within the range of the scanning session, will be a hyperbola signature. The point reflector concept introduces a number of assumptions and simplifications which lead to a specific statement: for a single GPR measurement and an isolated point reflector in space, the recorded trace will be the initially transmitted pulse shifted in time according to the time of the two-way travel of the signal from the GPR device to the target and back. With reference to Fig. 2(a), for a reflector located in point $p_r = (x_r, z_r)$ the shortest travel distance d_i will occur when GPR antenna is directly above it at $p_0 = (x_r, 0)$ (for all points first coordinate refers to the scanning direction axis and second coordinate refers to depth). For this scanning position, the time shift of the transmitted pulse is calculated as $t_0 = (2 \cdot d_0)/v = (2 \cdot z_r)/v$ where the 2 factor accounts for the back and forth travel and v is the wave propagation velocity in the examined space. For any other scanning position $p_i = (x_i, 0)$ travel distance d_i is calculated as $d_i = \sqrt{z_r^2 + (x_i - x_r)^2}$. Solving for the corresponding time delay, the following equation is derived:

$$t_i = \frac{2}{v} \cdot \sqrt{z_r^2 + (x_i - x_r)^2} \quad (2)$$

X axis of B-scans images and the scanning trajectory, as depicted on Fig. 2(a), coincide while Z axis of the physical world representation can be transformed to the Y axis of the B-scan image by applying Eq. 2. Unlike a learning approach, in the presented method, hyperbola templates, that will act as models of the class of reflection signatures originating from underground utilities, are not extracted from a set of positive samples but are rather generated based on theoretical Eq. 2. Taking a more careful look on this equation, two statements can be derived: (i) due to the z_r term for a given propagation velocity the shape of the generated template depends on the depth of the candidate utility and (ii) due to the $x_i - x_r$ term, that introduces the notion of relative distance from the x_r coordinate of the candidate utility, the slope of a template for a given depth does not

change. Hence, for any given depth z_r coordinate, hyperbola template needs to be computed only once and then it must be simply appropriately translated for each considered x_r coordinate, in order to be centered around it. These statements are graphically represented in Fig. 2(b) and lead to an efficient implementation of the proposed template generation. Instead of calculating the corresponding hyperbola template for each candidate position on the 2D image space it suffices to compute a dictionary of all templates for all discrete depths that fall within the device range and simply retrieve and transform the computed template around each considered position.

2.4 Hybrid Measure for Hyperbola Hypotheses

The next step of our method comprises the application of the hyperbola theoretical model on the real GPR measurements. Specifically, each peak detected in Sec. 2.1 constitutes a candidate hyperbola apex and the pre-computed hyperbola template that corresponds to the apex's respective coordinates in B-scan is retrieved from the dictionary. It should be noted that the theoretical model does not take into account any attenuation phenomena or the directionality of the antenna and therefore the hyperbola signature is expanding indefinitely around the apex. Since this is not the case in real data, it is necessary to define a minimum number of GPR traces (B-scan columns) around the candidate apex that the hyperbola signature is expected to be visible. A reasonable number for the following analysis is $N = 60$ traces. For each of those traces the peak with the measured time of occurrence closest to the theoretically computed time of the hyperbola model is selected. Application of the theoretical hyperbola model on real measurements is illustrated in Fig. 3. Then, the two following scores are introduced:

Fig. 3. From left to right: initial B-scan Image, per column detected peaks, hyperbola template computed for a considered apex marked with red color and closest peaks per column marked with green, extracted pulses corresponding to the closest peaks.

Geometric Similarity Score The geometric similarity score is computed as the sum of absolute differences between estimated time of occurrence for each trace and the actual detected time of the peak closest to the estimated model

among all peaks for the considered trace:

$$score_{similarity} = \sum_{x_i=x_0-N}^{x_0+N} |t_i(x_i, x_0, y_0) - t_{peak_i^*}| \quad (3)$$

where $peak_i^* = \arg \min_{peaks[x_i]} |t_i(x_i, x_0, y_0) - t_{peaks[x_i]}|$

The first measure captures only the geometric resemblance of 2D patterns shaped by peaks of actual measurements to automatically generated hyperbola models. However, it fails to discriminate between “positive” peaks corresponding to pulses actually originating from underground targets and “negative” peaks corresponding to pulses originating from underground clutter, artifacts of the scanning procedure, echoes, etc. It can be therefore argued that, if only the geometry measure is considered, patterns on which pulses that are not reflections of a certain underground utility contribute, can be mistakenly classified as reflection signatures.

Pulse Consistency Score In [17] a strict condition is imposed, demanding the waveforms of reflection pulses contributing to hyperbola atoms to directly resemble the stimulating wavelet initially transmitted by the GPR. This approach does not take into consideration the change of the characteristics (e.g. frequency) of the wavefield as it propagates in any medium. This change differs according to the electromagnetic characteristics of the medium of propagation. Besides, this approach does not account for any of the distortions that the signal might undergo while traveling and impinging on underground targets. Here, a much looser criterion is introduced that can be applied unchanged for signals travelling on various types of soil, reflecting on various types of underground targets and undergoing a reasonable amount of distortion. Instead of asking for reflection pulses to resemble the stimulating pulse, the requirement is for pulses contributing on a reflection signature of an underground utility to resemble to each other. Therefore, we make use of the features (i.e. DWT representations) extracted for each pulse around the selected peaks and we calculate the squared L2 norm between each other. The consistency score based on the calculation of squared L2 norm of the samples is expressed as follows:

$$score_{consistency} = \sum_{x_i=x_0-N}^{x_0+N} \sum_{x_j=x_0-N}^{x_0+N} \left\| dwt(pulse_i^*) - dwt(pulse_j^*) \right\|_2^2 \quad (4)$$

where $pulse_i^* = \arg \min_{peaks[x_i]} |t_i(x_i, x_0, y_0) - t_{peaks[x_i]}|$

and $pulse_j^* = \arg \min_{peaks[x_j]} |t_j(x_j, x_0, y_0) - t_{peaks[x_j]}|$

Naive calculation of the consistency score, as presented in Eq. 4, involves two summations among all the pulses participating in the hyperbola signature under consideration. However, squared L2 norm involved in the above calculations can

be expressed as a dot product: $\|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}\|_2^2 = (\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}) \cdot (\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y})^T$. By expanding the right part of this equation, $(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}) \cdot (\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y})^T = \|\mathbf{x}\|_2^2 + \|\mathbf{y}\|_2^2 - 2 \cdot \mathbf{x} \cdot \mathbf{y}^T$ it is derived that the calculation of the squared L2 norm of a vector subtraction can be expressed as two squared L2 norm calculations and one dot product calculation. This deduction, expanded for multiple vector subtractions, can benefit efficient calculation of score consistency. DWT coefficients of all pulses are gathered in a matrix $\mathbf{X} \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times n}$, where m is the number of pulses participating in the considered signature and n is the number of the coefficients in the DWT representation. In this format each row of the matrix is the vector representation of a pulse, $\mathbf{X}[i, :] = \text{dwt}(\text{pulse}_i)$, and the matrix multiplication $\mathbf{X} \cdot \mathbf{X}^T$ corresponds to calculation of the dot product of all possible combinations between participating pulses. Besides, per row summation of the squared matrix \mathbf{X}^2 equals to the squared norm of all the vector representations. Consequently, the two for loops of Eq. 4 can be fully vectorized and implemented as one matrix multiplication and one broadcast sum.

Final score The two introduced scores of the hybrid measure need to be combined in a single score that will be eventually utilized to discriminate between positive and negative hyperbola hypotheses. Two empirically defined max thresholds are utilized for the two scores. If a considered hypothesis exceeds any of them, then it is discarded. Remaining scores are normalized with respect to the max thresholds and a final score is computed by the following equation:

$$\text{score}_{final} = \sqrt{\left(\frac{\text{score}_{similarity}}{\text{max}_{similarity}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\text{score}_{consistency}}{\text{max}_{consistency}}\right)^2} \quad (5)$$

A non max suppression step is finally applied to provide final hyperbola detection. All the overlapping hypotheses are sorted according to their final score and the most prevailing ones are selected.

3 Evaluation

Fig. 4. From left to right: input B-scan image with 12 annotated hyperbola signatures originating from underground utilities, final detections provided by the complete detection pipeline, hypotheses that satisfy only the max similarity score criterion, hypotheses that satisfy only the max consistency score criterion.

The proposed method has been evaluated on data recorded from a dedicated IDS field site. An example of an input B-scan image along with the acquired results is provided in Fig. 4. As it is illustrated in that figure, the proposed method successfully detects 11 out of 12 reflection signatures with only 2 false positive detections. In the two last images of the same figure, intermediate results of signatures surviving the geometric similarity and the pulse consistency checks are provided. In both images a much bigger rate of false positive detections is examined. This is a result either of peaks of inconsistent pulses that resemble a hyperbola, or of consistent pulses that formulate patterns different from the hyperbola model in shape. As a conclusion, proposed method combines two loose criteria to provide a rather robust detector.

4 Conclusions

In this work, a novel hyperbola detection method has been developed based on the fusion of two scores in a single hybrid measure, that on the one hand controls the geometric characteristics of the recorded patterns and, on the other hand demands the consistency of the pulses that participate in the formulation of these patterns. The introduced method does not depend on any other parameters related to the type of soil on which the underground utilities are buried, yet for the creation of the dictionary of the hyperbolic theoretical models, the specifications of the utilized GPR antenna are considered. Proposed implementation makes use of vectorization to diminish computational burden. Overall the proposed method exhibited promising performance when examined on real data, an evaluation that will be extended with various GPR devices and types of soils in our future work.

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